

Energy-optimised cryogenic CO₂ capture for cement production decarbonisation: process design and techno-economic analysis

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Supplementary Material

Contents

S1. Liquid heat capacity prediction improvement	2
S2. Molecular sieve modelling and design	8
S3. Variable profiles calculation within a multi-stream heat exchanger	10
S4. Design and sizing of heat exchangers	13
S4.1 Plate-and-fin exchangers.....	13
S4.2 Plate heat exchangers.....	14
S4.3 Shell-and-tube heat exchangers	16
S5. Design and sizing of columns.....	18
S5.1 Water blowdown fraction in drying section	20
S6. Cost correlations and parameters for economic analysis.....	21
S7. Detailed energy and material balances for CCC-90	25
S8. Detailed energy and material balances for CCC-95	28
Nomenclature	31
References.....	34

S1. Liquid heat capacity prediction improvement

In the cryogenic CO₂ capture (CCC) process, reliable prediction of liquid heat capacities is essential for accurate energy balance calculations and process simulation. However, cubic equations of state, such as the volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR) adopted in this study or the classical Peng-Robinson (PR), generally provide poor predictions of liquid heat capacity (c_P^{liq}). To address this issue, the approach proposed by Diedrichs et al. (2006) was applied as follows to each species present in the liquid phase:

1. **Validation of ideal gas heat capacity (c_P^{ig}):** experimental c_P^{ig} data were collected to verify the accuracy of the default gPROMS Properties correlation across the operating temperature range (from -140°C to 200°C), as accurate c_P^{ig} representation is essential for correct c_P^{liq} prediction. If deviations were found, a re-fit of the c_P^{ig} correlation was performed.
2. **Improvement of c_P^{liq} predictions:** parameters l_0 , l_1 , and l_2 of the modified α -function proposed by Twu et al. (1991) (Equation 1) were fitted to vapour pressure (P^{sat}) and c_P^{liq} experimental data:

$$\alpha(T) = \left(\frac{T}{T_{cr}}\right)^{l_2 \cdot (l_1 - 1)} \cdot \exp\left\{l_0 \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{T}{T_{cr}}\right)^{l_2 \cdot l_1}\right]\right\} \quad (1)$$

where T is the temperature, T_{cr} is the critical temperature of the component, and l_0 , l_1 , and l_2 are component-specific parameters.

3. **Final check:** the modified VTPR was tested to ensure that phase equilibria and gas heat capacity (c_P^{gas}) predictions remained consistent with those of the standard VTPR.

Pseudo-experimental data for c_P^{ig} , P^{sat} , c_P^{liq} , and c_P^{gas} were retrieved from the NIST Chemistry WebBook (Linstrom and Mallard, 2001). Since the temperature within the process never falls below 130 K (-145°C), data were collected from this minimum value upwards. The fitted parameters and applicable temperature ranges are reported in Table 2 of the main text, while Figures S1-S4 illustrate the outcomes of the procedure.

Figure S1 compares c_P^{ig} values calculated with the gPROMS correlation against pseudo-experimental data in the 130-500 K range. The correlation adequately represents all components except isopentane, for which c_P^{ig} is overestimated below 200 K (-75°C). In this case, the default gPROMS expression was replaced with a second-order polynomial fit to experimental data using the least-squares method:

$$c_P^{ig}(T) = c_0 + c_1 \cdot T + c_2 \cdot T^2 \quad (2)$$

where T is temperature, and c_0 , c_1 , and c_2 are fitting parameters.

Figure S1. Comparison of ideal heat capacity prediction for selected species obtained by gPROMS Properties standard correlation against data from Linstrom and Mallard (2001).

The improvement achieved with the new correlation (NIST fit correlation) is presented in Table S1, which compares the c_P^{ig} values predicted by the default gPROMS correlation and by the new polynomial fit against the experimental data in the critical temperature range (130-300 K). As shown, the default correlation exhibits increasingly large deviations below 200 K (-75°C), reaching an overestimation of approximately 26% at the lowest temperature considered. In contrast, the new correlation provides an accurate representation of the experimental data across the entire 130-200 K interval, keeping the relative deviation below 0.3%. It also maintains good predictive performance at higher temperatures.

Table S1. Comparison of ideal heat capacity prediction for isopentane obtained by gPROMS Properties standard correlation and the new fitting correlation against experimental data from Linstrom and Mallard (2001).

Experimental data NIST		gPROMS correlation		NIST fit correlation	
Temperature [K]	c_P^{ig} [J/mol/K]	c_P^{ig} [J/mol/K]	Rel. error [%]	c_P^{ig} [J/mol/K]	Rel. error [%]
130	59.83	75.31	25.9%	59.72	-0.2%
140	63.57	75.87	19.4%	63.39	-0.3%
150	67.24	76.69	14.1%	67.04	-0.3%
160	70.85	77.81	9.8%	70.67	-0.3%
170	74.43	79.24	6.5%	74.28	-0.2%
180	77.96	81.00	3.9%	77.88	-0.1%
190	81.48	83.08	2.0%	81.46	0.0%
200	84.97	85.46	0.6%	85.02	0.1%
210	88.45	88.13	-0.4%	88.57	0.1%
220	91.93	91.05	-1.0%	92.09	0.2%
230	95.39	94.19	-1.3%	95.60	0.2%
240	98.86	97.50	-1.4%	99.10	0.2%
250	102.31	100.96	-1.3%	102.57	0.3%
260	105.77	104.54	-1.2%	106.03	0.2%
270	109.21	108.19	-0.9%	109.47	0.2%
280	112.66	111.89	-0.7%	112.89	0.2%
290	116.09	115.61	-0.4%	116.29	0.2%
300	119.52	119.34	-0.2%	119.68	0.1%

Figure S2 illustrates the improvements in c_P^{liq} prediction achieved with the developed thermodynamic framework by comparing VTPR with modified α -function, standard VTPR, and PR against experimental data. The modified VTPR substantially improves estimates, particularly for CO_2 , H_2O , isopentane and ethylene. Unlike PR and standard VTPR, which yield systematic deviations and incorrect trends, the modified VTPR more closely matches experimental data. Furthermore, the re-fit of c_P^{ig} for isopentane eliminated the anomalous decreasing trend of c_P^{liq} below 200 K.

Figures S3 and S4 compare the standard and modified VTPR in terms of c_P^{gas} and phase equilibria. The ability to reproduce c_P^{gas} and phase equilibria was preserved after fitting, with slight improvements for CO_2 solubility in water (top-right plot in Figure S4).

Figure S2. Comparison of liquid heat capacity prediction for selected species obtained by standard volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR), standard Peng-Robinson (PR), and VTPR with modified α -function, against data from Linstrom and Mallard (2001).

Figure S3. Comparison of gas heat capacity prediction for selected species obtained by standard volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR) and VTPR with modified α -function, against data from Linstrom and Mallard (2001).

Figure S4. Comparison of phase equilibria prediction obtained by standard volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR) and VTPR with modified α -function, against experimental data (●: Dalmolin et al., (2006); ■: Kurata, (1974); ▲: Besserer and Robinson (1975)).

S2. Molecular sieve modelling and design

A custom model was developed to simulate and size the molecular sieve used for flue gas drying, following the approach described in Towler and Sinnott (2021). The model serves two main purposes:

- Determining the required adsorbent mass and bed dimensions to meet the separation target within the allowable pressure drop.
- Estimating the thermal effect of exothermic H₂O adsorption, which influences CCC cooling requirements.

Although adsorption is inherently an unsteady process, a more steady flow of product gas is achieved in industry by operating units in pairs, with one bed adsorbing while the other regenerates. The system was therefore represented as a pseudo-continuous process, assuming thermal equilibrium between the outlet gas and the solid bed at the end of the adsorption step.

As represented in Figure S5, the molecular sieve model includes:

- 1 inlet material stream (wet gas).
- 2 outlet material streams (dry gas and adsorbate).

Figure S5. Scheme of the molecular sieve model.

Apart from the inlet stream connection, the required model inputs are:

- Number of parallel beds (N_b) in the adsorption stage of the cycle.
- Adsorption time (t_{ads}), i.e., the duration of the adsorption stage of the cycle.
- Either maximum allowable pressure drop across the bed (ΔP_b) or bed diameter (D_b).
- Adsorbent bed properties including water adsorption design capacity ($q_{H_2O}^{design}$), heat of water adsorption ($\Delta H_{ads,H_2O}$), saturated bed fraction (F_b), particle diameter (D_p), bed porosity (ϵ_b), bulk density ($\rho_{bulk,b}$), and heat capacity ($c_{p,b}$).

The model, defined by Equations 3-13, is presented for a single adsorption bed, but can be extended to N_b parallel units by dividing the inlet gas flow rate accordingly. Symbols \dot{m} , w and H correspond to mass flowrate, mass fraction, and mass enthalpy, respectively; superscripts “IN” and “OUT” indicate inlet and outlet streams, while the subscripts “G” and “A” refer to the gas and adsorbate phases, respectively.

For H₂O, the material balance assumes complete removal from the flue gas, consistent with the target of trace-level outlet concentration:

$$\dot{m}_G^{OUT} \cdot w_{H_2O,G}^{OUT} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{m}_A^{OUT} \cdot w_{H_2O,A}^{OUT} = \dot{m}_G^{IN} \cdot w_{H_2O,G}^{IN} \quad (4)$$

For all the other species i , which remain in the gas phase:

$$\dot{m}_G^{OUT} \cdot w_{i,G}^{OUT} = \dot{m}_G^{IN} \cdot w_{i,G}^{IN} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{m}_A^{OUT} \cdot w_{i,A}^{OUT} = 0 \quad (6)$$

The overall material balance is given by:

$$\dot{m}_G^{IN} = \dot{m}_G^{OUT} + \dot{m}_A^{OUT} \quad (7)$$

The required adsorbent mass per bed (m_b) is given by:

$$t_{ads} \cdot (\dot{m}_A^{OUT} \cdot w_{H_2O,A}^{OUT}) = m_b \cdot F_b \cdot q_{H_2O}^{design} \quad (8)$$

The corresponding bed volume (V_b), assuming a cylindrical geometry, is:

$$V_b = \frac{m_b}{\rho_{bulk,b}} = \frac{\pi D_b^2}{4} \cdot L_b \quad (9)$$

where D_b and L_b refer to the bed diameter and the bed length, respectively. The total height of the adsorption vessel is $L_b + 3$ m to account for internals (Cinti et al., 2018).

The overall energy balance considers an adiabatic bed and accounts for the heat of adsorption while avoiding double-counting the heat of water vaporisation ($\Delta H_{vap,H_2O}$):

$$\dot{m}_G^{IN} \cdot H_G^{IN} - (\dot{m}_G^{OUT} \cdot H_G^{OUT} + \dot{m}_A^{OUT} \cdot H_A^{OUT}) + \frac{m_b \cdot c_{p,b} \cdot (T_G^{IN} - T_G^{OUT})}{t_{ads}} \quad (10)$$

$$+ (\Delta H_{ads,H_2O} - \Delta H_{vap,H_2O}) \cdot (\dot{m}_A^{OUT} \cdot w_{H_2O,A}^{OUT}) = 0$$

$$\Delta H_{vap,H_2O} = H_{H_2O,G}^{IN} - H_{H_2O,A}^{OUT} \quad (11)$$

The pressure drop across the packed bed is estimated with Ergun's equation:

$$\frac{\Delta P_b}{L_b} = \frac{150 \cdot \mu_G \cdot v_G}{(D_p)^2} \frac{(1 - \varepsilon_b)^2}{(\varepsilon_b)^2} + \frac{1.75 \cdot \rho_G \cdot (v_G)^2 (1 - \varepsilon_b)}{D_p (\varepsilon_b)^2} \quad (12)$$

where the gas viscosity (μ_G) and density (ρ_G) are evaluated at the average temperature between inlet and outlet, and the superficial gas velocity (v_G) is calculated via:

$$v_G = \frac{4}{\pi(D_b)^2} \cdot \frac{\frac{\dot{m}_G^{IN}}{\rho_G^{IN}} + \frac{\dot{m}_G^{OUT}}{\rho_G^{OUT}}}{2} \quad (13)$$

Zeolite 3A was selected as the adsorbent material due to its higher selectivity for H₂O over CO₂ and its lower regeneration temperature compared to zeolite 4A (Kohl and Nielsen, 1997). The model parameters adopted in this study, together with the typical properties of adsorption beds packed with Zeolite 3A beads, are reported in Table S2.

Table S2. *Input parameters for the molecular sieve adsorption model.*

Variable		Value	Reference
Number beds adsorption (N_b)	-	7	
Adsorption time (t_{ads})	h	4	Cinti et al. (2018)
Pressure drop (ΔP_b)	bar	0.35	Kohl and Nielsen (1997)
Design capacity ($q_{H_2O}^{design}$)	kg _{H₂O} /kg _{adsorbent}	0.168	Cinti et al. (2018)
Heat of adsorption ($\Delta H_{ads,H_2O}$)	kJ/kg _{H₂O}	3500	Simo et al. (2009)
Saturated bed fraction (F_b)	-	0.75	Towler and Sinnott (2021)
Particle diameter (D_p)	m	0.0035	Kohl and Nielsen (1997)
Bed porosity (ε_b)	-	0.38	Kohl and Nielsen (1997)
Bulk density ($\rho_{bulk,b}$)	kg/m ³	710	Kohl and Nielsen (1997)
Heat capacity ($c_{p,b}$)	kJ/kg/K	1.045	Simo et al. (2009)

S3. Variable profiles calculation within a multi-stream heat exchanger

The gPROMS library model for the multi-stream heat exchanger (MSHX) does not include the zone analysis, which is required to verify that no internal temperature crossover occurs and to determine key variables for preliminary sizing. For this reason, a post-processing algorithm was developed (Figure S6) to generate the relevant variable profiles within the unit. The specific objectives are:

- Dividing the MSHX into z zones defined by temperature or heat exchanged intervals.
- Determining, for each zone z , the thermal power exchanged by stream k ($\dot{Q}_{z,k}$), the minimum temperature approach (ΔT_{min}), and the logarithmic mean temperature difference ($LMTD_z$).

Cold streams (to be heated) and hot streams (to be cooled) are denoted by the superscripts ‘‘COLD’’ and ‘‘HOT’’, respectively. The following discussion focuses on the cold side, although the same reasoning applies to the hot side as well.

The composite curves represent the overall heat balance of the MSHX. The hot composite curve describes the total heat that must be removed, obtained by summing the enthalpy changes of all hot streams. Conversely, the cold composite curve represents the total heat that must be supplied, obtained by summing all cold streams. The division of the MSHX into zones requires identifying the temperatures at which the hot and cold composite curves change slope, corresponding to potential pinch points. These slope changes occur when the heat capacity flowrate (CP) of either side changes:

$$CP = \sum_k \dot{m}_k \cdot c_{p,k} \quad (14)$$

From Equation 14, it is evident that CP changes when:

- A stream enters or exits the MSHX, at its inlet ($T_{IN,k}^{COLD}$) or outlet ($T_{OUT,k}^{COLD}$) temperatures.
- A phase change occurs, modifying the $c_{p,k}$. Phase transitions are identified by the bubble point ($T_{bubble,k}^{COLD}$) and dew point ($T_{dew,k}^{COLD}$), which depend on the stream composition (w_k^{COLD}) and are evaluated at the average pressure between inlet ($P_{IN,k}^{COLD}$) and outlet ($P_{OUT,k}^{COLD}$).

Accordingly, for each stream k , a vector of characteristic temperatures (T_k^{COLD}) is constructed and sorted in ascending order to facilitate zone identification. In some cases, a stream may enter as a biphasic mixture, such that $T_{bubble,k}^{COLD}$ and/or $T_{dew,k}^{COLD}$ fall outside the interval $[T_{IN,k}^{COLD}, T_{OUT,k}^{COLD}]$. To ensure dimensional consistency and maintain generality in the algorithm, the following substitutions are applied in such cases:

$$T_{bubble,k}^{COLD} = T_{IN,k}^{COLD} \quad (15)$$

$$T_{dew,k}^{COLD} = T_{OUT,k}^{COLD} \quad (16)$$

considering that for a cold stream $T_{bubble,k}^{COLD} < T_{dew,k}^{COLD}$ and $T_{IN,k}^{COLD} < T_{OUT,k}^{COLD}$.

Figure S6. Conceptual flow diagram of the algorithm developed to calculate variable profiles within the multi-stream heat exchanger (MSHX).

The vectors T_k^{COLD} from all cold streams are merged into a single vector of characteristic temperatures (T_{cz}^{COLD}), sorted in ascending order. This defines the subdivision of the MSHX into a number of cold zones, denoted as cz .

The duty exchanged in zone cz ($\dot{Q}_{cz,k}^{COLD}$) and the cumulative duty up to that zone ($\dot{Q}_{cum,cz,k}^{COLD}$) are computed for each stream k as:

\forall COLD stream k , \forall COLD zone cz

$$\begin{cases} \dot{Q}_{cz,k}^{COLD} = \dot{m}_k^{COLD} \cdot (H_{cz,k}^{COLD} - H_{cz-1,k}^{COLD}) & \text{if } T_{cz}^{COLD} \in [T_{IN,k}^{COLD}, T_{OUT,k}^{COLD}] \\ \dot{Q}_{cz,k}^{COLD} = 0 & \text{if } T_{cz}^{COLD} \notin [T_{IN,k}^{COLD}, T_{OUT,k}^{COLD}] \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$H_{cz,k}^{COLD} = f(T_{cz}^{COLD}, P_{cz,k}^{COLD}, w_k^{COLD}) \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{cum,cz,k}^{COLD} = \dot{Q}_{cz,k}^{COLD} + \dot{Q}_{cum,cz-1,k}^{COLD} \quad \forall \text{ COLD stream } k, \forall \text{ COLD zone } cz \quad (19)$$

The total cumulative heat duty exchanged by all cold streams up to zone cz is given by:

$$\dot{Q}_{cum,cz}^{COLD} = \sum_k \dot{Q}_{cum,cz,k}^{COLD} \quad \forall \text{ COLD zone } cz \quad (20)$$

Once these variables are computed for both the hot and cold side, the vectors $\dot{Q}_{cum,cz}^{COLD}$ and $\dot{Q}_{cum,hz}^{HOT}$ are merged and sorted, to give the total cumulative duty vector ($\dot{Q}_{cum,z}$). This procedure discretises the total MSHX duty into z global zones in which the heat transferred is given by:

$$\dot{Q}_z = \dot{Q}_{cum,z} + \dot{Q}_{cum,z-1} \quad \forall \text{ zone } z \quad (21)$$

At this stage $\dot{Q}_{z,k}^{COLD}$ and T_z^{COLD} are recomputed in each new global zone z according to a formulation that is analogous to Equations 17-18:

\forall COLD stream k , \forall zone z

$$\begin{cases} \dot{Q}_{z,k}^{COLD} = \dot{m}_k^{COLD} \cdot (H_{z,k}^{COLD} - H_{z-1,k}^{COLD}) & \text{if } T_z^{COLD} \in [T_{IN,k}^{COLD}, T_{OUT,k}^{COLD}] \\ \dot{Q}_{z,k}^{COLD} = 0 & \text{if } T_z^{COLD} \notin [T_{IN,k}^{COLD}, T_{OUT,k}^{COLD}] \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

$$H_{z,k}^{COLD} = f(T_z^{COLD}, P_{z,k}^{COLD}, w_k^{COLD}) \quad (23)$$

with the consistency condition:

$$\dot{Q}_z = \sum_k \dot{Q}_{z,k}^{COLD} \quad \forall \text{ zone } z \quad (24)$$

The pressure drop up to the zone z is assumed to be linearly distributed according to the share of cumulative heat exchanged by the stream k up to zone z with respect to its total heat duty exchanged (\dot{Q}_k^{COLD}) (Picón-Núñez et al., 2002):

$$P_{z,k}^{COLD} = P_{IN,k}^{COLD} - (P_{IN,k}^{COLD} - P_{OUT,k}^{COLD}) \frac{\dot{Q}_{cum,z,k}^{COLD}}{\dot{Q}_k^{COLD}} \quad \forall \text{ zone } z \quad (25)$$

Finally, the temperature difference in each zone z (ΔT_z), ΔT_{min} , and $LMTD_z$ are obtained as:

$$\Delta T_z = T_z^{HOT} - T_z^{COLD} \quad \forall \text{ zone } z \quad (26)$$

$$\Delta T_{min} = \min(\Delta T_z) \quad \forall \text{ zone } z \quad (27)$$

$$LMTD_z = \frac{\Delta T_z - \Delta T_{z-1}}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_z}{\Delta T_{z-1}}\right)} \quad \forall \text{ zone } z \quad (28)$$

S4. Design and sizing of heat exchangers

The heat exchangers in the CCC process were selected according to the nature of the fluids and operating conditions:

- Plate-and-fin exchangers for the multi-stream heat exchanger (MSHX) and distillation column reboiler.
- Plate heat exchangers for the compressor intercoolers, the flue gas cooler (HX1 in Figure 5 of the main text) and the isopentane cooler (HX2 in Figure 5 of the main text).
- Shell-and-tube exchangers for heat exchange involving slurries (SLURRY COOLER and MELTER), as well as for the distillation condenser and the high-pressure CO₂ cooler (HX3 in Figure 5 of the main text).

The sizing procedure depends on the exchanger type. For plate-and-fin exchangers, a dedicated volumetric approach is adopted. For plate and shell-and-tube exchangers, the sizing is based on the required exchange area (A_{exc}) which is determined once the thermal power exchanged (\dot{Q}) and the logarithmic mean temperature difference ($LMTD$) are obtained from process simulations:

$$A_{exc} = \frac{\dot{Q}}{U_{exc} \cdot LMTD} \quad (29)$$

This calculation requires the definition of an overall heat transfer coefficient (U_{exc}), which depends on the fluid pair and the exchanger configuration.

S4.1 Plate-and-fin exchangers

The sizing of plate-and-fin exchangers aims at determining the exchanger volume V_{exc} and follows the B-value method described in ESDU 97 006 guidelines (ESDU, 2003).

For a multi-stream exchanger (i.e., the MSHX), the procedure relies on the zone analysis described in Section S3, which provides the variable profiles for each exchanger zone z . The overall volumetric heat transfer coefficient ($B_{exc,z}$) of each zone z containing k streams (either hot or cold) is:

$$\frac{\dot{Q}_z}{B_{exc,z}} = \sum_k \frac{\dot{Q}_{z,k}}{\beta_k} \quad (30)$$

where \dot{Q}_z is the total heat transferred in zone z , $\dot{Q}_{z,k}$ is the heat transferred by stream k in the zone z and β_k is the local volumetric heat transfer coefficient for stream k (Table S3), based on the fluid type. The volume of each zone z is computed as:

$$V_z = \frac{\dot{Q}_z}{B_{exc,z} \cdot LMTD_z} \quad (31)$$

The total exchanger volume V_{exc} , is finally calculated by summing all zone volumes and adding 15% for headers and distributors:

$$V_{exc} = 1.15 \sum_z V_z \quad (32)$$

For a two-stream exchanger (i.e., the distillation reboiler), the same methodology applies but with only one global zone. The overall volumetric heat transfer coefficient (B_{exc}) is computed from the β_k values (Table S3) of the two streams as:

$$\frac{1}{B_{exc}} = \frac{1}{\beta_1} + \frac{1}{\beta_2} \quad (33)$$

The total exchanger volume V_{exc} , again including 15% allowance for header and distributor, is:

$$V_{exc} = 1.15 \frac{\dot{Q}}{B_{exc} \cdot LMTD} \quad (34)$$

Table S3. Local volumetric heat transfer coefficients assumed for plate-and-fin exchanger sizing (ESDU, 2003).

Stream (Figure 5)	Fluid type	Selected β_k [kW/m ³ /K]
1	Air-type gaseous (low pressure)	60
Distillation residue	Light hydrocarbon boiling	1400
7	Air-type gaseous (low pressure)	60
14	Air-type gaseous (low pressure)	60
27	Light hydrocarbon boiling	1400
34	Light hydrocarbon liquid	1100
38	Light hydrocarbon condensing	1400
41	Light hydrocarbon boiling	1400
46	Light hydrocarbon boiling	1400

S4.2 Plate heat exchangers

A preliminary method for determining the U_{exc} in plate heat exchangers is provided by Towler and Sinnott (2021). The required exchange surface (A_{exc}) can be computed assuming a tentative overall heat transfer coefficient (U^*):

$$A_{exc} = \frac{\dot{Q}}{U^* \cdot LMTD} \quad (35)$$

The main design parameters for plate exchangers are listed in Table S4 along with their typical values (Shah and Sekulic, 2003).

Table S4. Design parameters for plate exchanger sizing and typical values.

Variable	Range	
Plate length (L_{pl})	m	0.4-5.0
Plate width (W_{pl})	m	0.07-1.20
Plate spacing (S_{pl})	mm	1.5-7.0
Plate thickness (s_{pl})	mm	0.5-1.2

The plate area (A_{pl}), the hydraulic equivalent diameter (D_{eq}), the number of total plates (N_{pl}), and the number of channels per pass ($N_{ch,pass}$) are computed as:

$$A_{pl} = L_{pl} \cdot W_{pl} \quad (36)$$

$$D_{eq} = 2 \cdot S_{pl} \quad (37)$$

$$N_{pl} = \frac{A_{exc}}{A_{pl}} \quad (38)$$

$$N_{ch,pass} = (N_{pl} - 1)/2 \quad (39)$$

with N_{pl} rounded to the nearest odd number.

The film heat transfer coefficient for stream k is estimated with the correlation:

$$h_k = \frac{k_k}{D_{eq}} 0.26(Re_k)^{0.65}(Pr_k)^{0.4} \quad (40)$$

where the dimensionless Re_k and Pr_k numbers are based on density (ρ_k), viscosity (μ_k), thermal conductivity (k_k) and specific heat ($c_{p,k}$) evaluated at the average of inlet and outlet conditions:

$$Re_k = \frac{\rho_k \cdot v_{ch,k} \cdot D_{eq}}{\mu_k} \quad (41)$$

$$Pr_k = \frac{\mu_k \cdot c_{p,k}}{k_k} \quad (42)$$

and the channel velocity ($v_{ch,k}$) is:

$$v_{ch,k} = \frac{\dot{m}_k}{\rho_k \cdot S_{pl} \cdot W_{pl} \cdot N_{ch,pass}} \quad (43)$$

Finally, the overall heat transfer coefficient (U_{exc}) is obtained by combining resistances on both exchanger sides $k1$ and $k2$, including the fouling factors ($C_{f,k}$):

$$\frac{1}{U_{exc}} = \frac{1}{h_{k1}} + \frac{1}{C_{f,k1}} + \frac{S_{pl}}{k_{pl}} + \frac{1}{h_{k2}} + \frac{1}{C_{f,k2}} \quad (44)$$

If the calculated U_{exc} agrees with the tentative U^* within 0 and +10% error, the sizing is accepted; otherwise, U^* or the exchanger design must be revised.

The pressure drop due to friction on the plate ($\Delta P_{pl,k}$) is estimated as:

$$\Delta P_{pl,k} = 8j_k \frac{L_{pl} \cdot \rho_k \cdot (v_{ch,k})^2}{D_{eq}} \quad (45)$$

with j_k depending on plate geometry. As a preliminary approximation in turbulent flow:

$$j_k = 0.6(Re_k)^{-0.3} \quad (46)$$

The transition from laminar to turbulent flow will normally occur at a Re_k of 100-400, depending on the plate design. Pressure losses at the ports ($\Delta P_{port,k}$) are also included:

$$\Delta P_{port,k} = 1.3 \frac{\rho_k \cdot (v_{port,k})^2}{2} \quad (47)$$

where the velocity through the port ($v_{port,k}$) is:

$$v_{port,k} = \frac{4 \cdot \dot{m}_k}{\rho_k \cdot \pi (D_{port})^2} \quad (48)$$

As an example, U_{exc} calculations are presented for the 5th intercooler of the Refrigerant 1 compressor in the CCC-90 configuration, considering a stainless-steel plate heat exchanger with $k_{pl} = 16 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$ (Towler and Sinnott, 2021). With the fluid properties and the plate exchanger design parameters reported in Table S5, the calculated overall heat transfer coefficient is $U_{exc} = 670.7 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$, which is well within the +10% error. The overall pressure drop, calculated as the sum of $\Delta P_{pl,k}$ and $\Delta P_{port,k}$, is estimated as 0.101 bar on the Refrigerant 1 (gas) side and 0.044 bar for the water (liquid), consistent with the assumption for compressor intercoolers.

Table S5. Stream properties and plate exchanger design parameters for the 5th intercooler of the Refrigerant 1 compressor in the CCC-90 configuration.

Stream properties				Exchanger design		
Variable		Refrigerant 1	Water	Variable	Value	
Flowrate (\dot{m}_k)	kg/s	80.35	78.18	Heat duty (\dot{Q})	MW _{th}	3.27
Density (ρ_k)	kg/s	15.58	995.53	LMTD	°C	9.10
Viscosity (μ_k)	N·s/m ²	$1.088 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.046 \cdot 10^{-5}$	Tent. coefficient (U^*)	W/m ² /K	670
Thermal cond. (k_k)	W/m/K	0.0293	0.6141	Plate length (L_{pl})	m	1.4
Specific heat ($c_{p,k}$)	J/kg/K	2043.3	4179.8	Plate width (W_{pl})	m	0.7
Fouling factor ($C_{f,k}$)	W/m ² /K	12000	8000	Plate spacing (S_{pl})	mm	4.6
Port diameter (D_{port})	m	0.60	0.20	Plate thickness (s_{pl})	mm	1.0

From this analysis, a representative value of $U_{exc} = 650 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$ was selected for heat exchange between a mixed refrigerant and cooling water in compressor intercoolers. Using the same approach, the U_{exc} adopted for plate exchanger sizing in the other cases are reported in Table S6.

Table S6. Overall surface heat transfer coefficients assumed for plate exchanger sizing.

Variable	Value	
U_{exc} for Refrigerant 1 compressor intercoolers	W/m ² /K	650
U_{exc} for Refrigerant 2 compressor intercooler	W/m ² /K	650
U_{exc} for flue gas cooler (HX1)	W/m ² /K	180
U_{exc} for isopentane cooler (HX2)	W/m ² /K	1700

S4.3 Shell-and-tube heat exchangers

Shell-and-tube heat exchangers are employed for the distillation condenser, the high-pressure CO₂ cooler (HX3), and the SLURRY COOLER and MELTER, due to the presence of slurries that preclude

the use of plate or plate-and-fin exchangers. The overall heat transfer coefficient (U_{exc}) for the shell-and-tube exchangers is obtained by summing the resistances on both shell (sh) and tube (t) sides including the fouling factors (C_f) as in the following (Towler and Sinnott, 2021):

$$\frac{1}{U_{exc}} = \frac{1}{h_{sh}} + \frac{1}{C_{f,sh}} + \frac{D_{ext} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{D_{ext}}{D_{int}}\right)}{2 \cdot k_t} + \frac{D_{ext}}{D_{int}} \frac{1}{h_t} + \frac{1}{C_{f,t}} \quad (49)$$

where d_{ext} and d_{int} are the external and internal diameter of the tubes, respectively, and k_t is the thermal conductivity of the tubes. The calculations were performed considering that all shell-and-tube exchangers are in stainless steel ($k_t = 16 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$), with typical dimensions of $d_{ext} = 32 \text{ mm}$ and $d_{int} = 27.8 \text{ mm}$, corresponding to a wall thickness of 2.1 mm (Towler and Sinnott, 2021).

The heat transfer coefficient on the shell (h_{sh}) and the tube side (h_t) as well as the C_f were retrieved from Peters et al. (2003), within the ranges reported for the relevant fluids. Conservative assumptions were applied in the presence of solids: for diluted slurries (5-10%_{mass}), the lower bound of h and upper bound of C_f were used, while for concentrated slurries in the MELTER, h was halved and the maximum C_f was assumed. The selected U_{exc} values from this analysis are reported in Table S7.

Table S7. Overall surface heat transfer coefficients selection for shell-and-tube exchanger sizing (Peters et al., 2003).

	HX3	SLURRY COOLER	MELTER	DIST Condenser
Shell stream	Cooling water	Refrigerant 1	Refrigerant 2	Condensing CO₂
Fluid type	Water, liquid	Light organics vap.	Light organics cond.	Light organics cond.
h (W/m ² /K)	5000	2200	3000	3000
C_f (W/m ² /K)	10000	10000	20000	20000
Tube stream	Compressed CO₂	Diluted slurry	Concentrated slurry	Refrigerant 2
Fluid type	Gas (P = 100 bar)	Light organic liquid	Light organic liquid	Light organics vap.
h (W/m ² /K)	500	1500	750	2200
C_f (W/m ² /K)	10000	5000	5000	10000
Calc. U_{exc} (W/m²/K)	350	591	437	860
Selec. U_{exc} (W/m²/K)	350	600	450	850

S5. Design and sizing of columns

Several column units are employed throughout the CCC process, namely the direct contact cooler (DCC), the water scrubbing and cooling columns (DRY1 and DRY2), the desublimation exchanger (DES), and the distillation column (DIST).

For all columns, the diameter was determined assuming a flooding factor of 0.8. When a single column would exceed a diameter of 5 m, two parallel units were considered. Packed column heights are calculated based on the number of equilibrium ideal stages and the height equivalent theoretical plate (*HETP*), estimated by gPROMS using built-in correlations depending on packing type, material, and dimension. For tray columns, the number of real stages was obtained from the ideal stages using a column efficiency, with the total height derived from tray spacing (S_{tray}). In both cases, 3 m were added to account for internals. The main design variables are summarised in Table S8.

Table S8. Design variables for the sizing of columns.

	CCC-90					CCC-95				
Variable	DCC	DRY1	DRY2	DES	DIST	DCC	DRY1	DRY2	DES	DIST
Nr. units	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1
Type	Packed	Packed	Packed	Packed	Tray	Packed	Packed	Packed	Packed	Tray
Efficiency %	-	-	-	35	65	-	-	-	35	65
Ideal stages	5	6	6	5	11	5	6	6	5	11
Real stages	5	6	6	14	17	5	6	6	14	17
$HETP/S_{tray}$ m	0.90	0.90	0.90	1.35	0.72	0.90	0.90	0.90	1.35	0.73
Diameter m	4.59	3.77	3.31	3.74	1.69	4.59	3.77	3.28	3.74	1.73
Height m	7.50	8.40	8.40	21.90	13.08	7.50	8.40	8.40	21.90	13.22

DCC, DRY1, and DRY2 are modelled as packed columns with 5, 6, and 6 equilibrium stages, respectively, using 50 mm (2-inch) metal Pall® rings as packing material.

The DES unit is a hybrid spray-bubble tower. A rigorous distributed model including detailed heat and mass transfer with column hydraulics would be required for detailed simulation and sizing, which is beyond the scope of this work. Instead, following Asgharian et al. (2025), DES is modelled as 5 equilibrium stages, each comprising a Mixer and Separator sequence in which gPROMS computes solid-liquid-vapour equilibria. The gas phase is directed to the stage above, while the solid and liquid phases are sent to the stage below.

For preliminary vessel sizing, DES is treated as a packed column with 5 equilibrium stages containing Raschig Super-Rings of the largest available size (75 mm, 3 inch), which correspond to the least efficient packing (i.e., highest *HETP*). To increase conservativeness, a column efficiency of 35% was assumed, resulting in a larger estimated column volume.

The operating pressure of DIST is an important design variable with multiple implications for the process energy demand. Increasing pressure reduces both condenser duty and CO₂ compression power, but also makes separation more challenging, requiring a higher number of stages and leading to greater CO₂ losses in the residue to maintain the reboiler temperature fixed to 100°C. This, in turn, increases the recycle flowrate of the distillation residue (stream #34 in Figure 5), with a consequent rise in the specific energy requirements of the process.

The influence of distillation pressure on the process energy penalty was investigated in the range 18–33 bar, while maintaining a fixed CO₂ purity target of 99.9%_{mass}. First, the sensitivity of condenser duty to the number of ideal stages was analysed at each pressure, with the optimal feed stage selected in each case (Figure S7). The number of ideal stages was then fixed at the point at which the condenser duty flattened, since additional stages would result in oversizing without appreciable performance improvement.

Figure S7. Sensitivity of distillation condenser duty to the number of ideal stages at different distillation pressures. The selected number of ideal stages corresponding to each pressure is highlighted with a black circle.

The corresponding column designs, defined by pressure, number of stages, and feed stage, were implemented in the CCC flowsheet, followed by process re-optimisation as described in Section 2.6 of the main text.

The results (Figure S8) show that distillation pressure has only a modest impact on the overall energy penalty, which remains within 1.19–1.20 MJ_e/kgCO₂ across the investigated range. Nonetheless, a minimum region can be identified between 24 and 27 bar. Between these alternatives, 24 bar was selected as the reference pressure, as it results in lower process flowrates and, consequently, smaller equipment sizes and reduces capital expenditures (CAPEX). The corresponding column configuration comprises 11 ideal stages, with the feed introduced above stage 9.

Figure S8. Sensitivity analysis of cryogenic capture energy penalty as a function of distillation operating pressure.

S5.1 Water blowdown fraction in drying section

One stage of the CCC drying section involves water removal from the flue gas using chilled water in DRY1. The chilled water is regenerated in DRY2, where a fraction of the cold, dry lean gas (stream #15, Figure 5) cools the water exiting DRY1 before it is recirculated. To prevent water accumulation in the closed loop between DRY1 and DRY2, a blowdown stream (stream #12) is introduced. As shown in Figure S9, the blowdown fraction is fixed at 0.015, which minimises the temperature of the gas exiting DRY1 (stream #6) and, consequently, its water content before the molecular sieve.

Figure S9. Effect of water blowdown fraction on the temperature of the gas exiting DRY1.

S6. Cost correlations and parameters for economic analysis

The cost correlations used to estimate the equipment cost (EC) of various process units are detailed in Table S9, along with the corresponding scaling parameters and installation factors (IF) used to compute the bare erected cost (BEC). All equipment employed in the CCC process is assumed to be made of stainless steel, due to its compatibility with process species and its ability to withstand cryogenic temperatures. The only exception is the plate-and-fin heat exchangers, which are typically made of aluminium (ESDU, 2003).

For equipment such as vertical vessels, pumps and shell-and-tube exchangers, the IF is expressed as a function of the pressure factor (PF) and the material factor (MF) according to:

$$IF = f_1 + f_2 \cdot PF \cdot MF \quad (50)$$

where the parameters f_1 , f_2 , and the corresponding values of PF and MF are taken from Turton et al. (2018) based on equipment type.

The EC correlation for plate heat exchangers in Table S9 refers to gasketed-plate exchangers, which operate up to 30 bar (Shah and Sekulic, 2003). For higher-pressure applications, welded-plate exchangers, capable of withstanding up to 40 bar (Shah and Sekulic, 2003), were assumed. The latter are estimated to be 25% more expensive than gasketed-plate exchangers (Peters et al., 2003).

The EC for 2- and 4-7-stream plate-and-fin heat exchangers was derived from the cost functions per unit exchanger volume reported in ESDU (2003), fitted using the following expression:

$$EC(\pounds_{1997}) = 10^{a_0 + a_1 \cdot \log_{10}(V_{exc}) + a_2 \cdot [\log_{10}(V_{exc})]^2} \quad (51)$$

where a_0 , a_1 , and a_2 are fitting parameters, and V_{exc} is the exchanger volume.

These correlations are valid for exchanger volumes between 0.5 and 11 m³. For larger exchangers, the cost was conservatively estimated by multiplying the total volume by the cost per unit volume at 11 m³, equal to 11600 £/m³ for a 2-stream exchanger and 13500 £/m³ for 4-7-stream exchangers. The EC values correspond to exchangers operating at pressures below 25 bar; for higher pressures, the EC was corrected using the pressure factors provided in ESDU (2003).

For sieve trays, the quantity factor (QF), defined as a function of the number of trays (N_{tray}), was applied only when $N_{tray} < 20$, as follows:

$$QF = 10^{0.4771 + 0.08516 \log_{10}(N_{tray}) - 0.3473 [\log_{10}(N_{tray})]^2} \quad (52)$$

Finally, as the BEC correlations from Turton et al. (2018) already include indirect costs, these were adjusted by deflating the calculated BEC by 14% to avoid double-counting.

Table S9. Cost correlations and installation factors for the various process units as a function of scaling parameters. All costs were then updated to €₂₀₂₄ with the CEPCI for January 2024 (795.4) and exchange rates of 0.91 €/€ and 1.18 €/£.

Process unit	Parameter	Correlation	Material	IF	Reference	
Blower	\dot{W}_{fluid} [kW]	$EC[\$_{2001}] = 10^{2.2897+1.3604 \log_{10}(\dot{W})-0.1027[\log_{10}(\dot{W})]^2}$	SS	5.7	Turton et al. (2018)	
Compressor	\dot{W}_{fluid} [kW]	$EC[\$_{2001}] = 10^{2.2897+1.3604 \log_{10}(\dot{W})-0.1027[\log_{10}(\dot{W})]^2}$	SS	5.7	Turton et al. (2018)	
Fan	\dot{V}^{IN} [m ³ /h] \dot{W}_{shaft} [kW]	$EC[M\text{€}_{2014}] = 31.1 \cdot 10^{-3} \left(\frac{\dot{V}}{25000} \right)^{0.5} + 19.1 \cdot 10^{-3} \left(\frac{\dot{W}}{75} \right)^{0.65}$	-	1.4	De Lena et al. (2019)	
Pump	\dot{W}_{shaft} [kW]	$EC[\$_{2001}] = 10^{3.3892+0.0536 \log_{10}(\dot{W})+0.1538[\log_{10}(\dot{W})]^2}$	SS	Eq. 50	Turton et al. (2018)	
CO ₂ pump	\dot{W}_{shaft} [kW]	$EC[M\text{€}_{2011}] = 1.66 \left(\frac{\dot{W}}{1200} \right)^{0.85}$	SS	1.667	Cinti et al. (2018)	
Electric heater	\dot{Q}_{el} [kW]	$EC[£_{2018}] = 50(\dot{Q}_{el})$	-	2.4	Element Energy (2018)	
Electric Drive	\dot{W}_{shaft} [kW]	$EC[\$_{2001}] = 10^{1.956+1.7142 \log_{10}(\dot{W})-0.2282[\log_{10}(\dot{W})]^2}$	-	1.5	Turton et al. (2018)	
Plate heat exchanger	A_{exc} [m ²]	$EC[\$_{2010}] = 1600 + 210(A)^{0.95}$ $EC[\$_{2010}] = 1.25 \cdot [1600 + 210(A)^{0.95}]$	$P \leq 30 \text{ bar}$ $P > 30 \text{ bar}$	SS	2.88	Towler and Sinnott (2021)
Shell&Tube heat exchanger (fl. head)	A_{exc} [m ²]	$EC[\$_{2001}] = 10^{4.8306-0.8509 \log_{10}(A)+0.3187[\log_{10}(A)]^2}$	SS	Eq. 50	Turton et al. (2018)	
Plate&Fin heat exchanger (2 streams)	V_{exc} [m ³]	$EC[£_{1997}] = 10^{4.42111+0.470673 \log_{10}(V)+0.178846[\log_{10}(V)]^2}$ $EC[£_{1997}] = 11600 \cdot V$	$V \leq 11 \text{ m}^3$ $V > 11 \text{ m}^3$	Al	1.5	ESDU (2003) Magli et al. (2022)
Plate&Fin heat exchanger (4-7 streams)	V_{exc} [m ³]	$EC[£_{1997}] = 10^{4.67039+0.378547 \log_{10}(V)+0.105692[\log_{10}(V)]^2}$ $EC[£_{1997}] = 13500 \cdot V$	$V \leq 11 \text{ m}^3$ $V > 11 \text{ m}^3$	Al	1.5	ESDU (2003) Magli et al. (2022)
Solid separator	\dot{m}_{solid}^{IN} [kg/s]	$EC[M\text{€}_{2021}] = 0.2 \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{19.9} \right)^{0.6}$	SS	2.83	Towler and Sinnott (2021) Asgharian et al. (2025)	

Table S9. Cost correlations and installation factors for the various process units as a function of scaling parameters. All costs were then updated to €₂₀₂₄ with the CEPCI for January 2024 (795.4) and exchange rates of 0.91 €/€ and 1.18 €/£ (continues from previous page).

Process unit	Parameter	Correlation	Material	IF	Reference
Vertical vessel	$V_{vessel}[\text{m}^3]$	$EC[\$_{2001}] = 10^{3.4974+0.4485 \log_{10}(V)+0.1074[\log_{10}(V)]^2}$	SS	Eq. 50	Turton et al. (2018)
Column packing	$V_{packing}[\text{m}^3]$	$EC[\$_{2001}] = 10^{2.4493+0.9744 \log_{10}(V)+0.0055[\log_{10}(V)]^2}$	SS	7.1	Turton et al. (2018)
Packed column		$BEC = BEC_{vessel} + BEC_{packing}$			
Sieve trays	$A[\text{m}^2]$ $N_{tray}[-]$	$EC[\$_{2001}] = N_{tray} \cdot QF \cdot 10^{2.9949+0.4465 \log_{10}(A)+0.3961[\log_{10}(A)]^2}$	SS	1.8	Turton et al. (2018)
Tray column		$BEC = BEC_{vessel} + BEC_{trays}$			
Molecular sieve	$m_b[\text{kg}]$	$BEC = BEC_{vessel} + 3.6 \text{ €/kg} \cdot m$			Cinti et al. (2018)

The framework of variable OPEX used for the comparison between CCC-90 and other low-carbon technologies is summarised in Table S10.

Table S10. Assumptions for OPEX calculation in the comparison between cryogenic CO₂ capture and other low-carbon technologies.

Variable OPEX			Reference
Raw meal	€/t _{Raw Meal}	3.012	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Coal	€/GJ _{LHV}	3.00	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Natural gas	€/GJ _{LHV}	10.0	IEA (2024)
Electricity	€/MWh _{el}	125.0	Eurostat (2025)
Steam (from waste heat)	€/MWh _{th}	8.50	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Steam (from natural gas boiler)	€/MWh _{th}	41.79	Anantharaman et al. (2017)
Cooling water	€/m ³	0.02	Cormos (2022)
Refrigerated water (15-25°C)	€/m ³	0.14	Estimated
Cooling water make-up	€/m ³	0.39	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Process water	€/m ³	6.65	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Ammonia SCNR	€/t _{NH₃}	130.0	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Isopentane make-up	€/t _{isop}	1200.0	ChemAnalyst (2025)
MEA	€/t _{MEA}	1450.0	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
NaOH DeSO _x	€/t _{NaOH}	370.0	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
CO ₂ Transport and Storage	€/t _{CO₂,prod}	35.0	d'Amore et al. (2021)

The OPEX of steam produced by a natural gas boiler was estimated as in Anantharaman et al. (2017) by considering an investment and maintenance costs of 1.3 €/MWh_{th} and assuming a boiler efficiency of 90%. After adjustment to 2024 values with the CEPCI index, the OPEX is given by:

$$OPEX_{boiler\ steam} = \frac{CEPCI_{2024}}{CEPCI_{2014}} \cdot 1.3 + OPEX_{natural\ gas} \frac{3.6}{0.9} \quad (53)$$

S7. Detailed energy and material balances for CCC-90

For the CCC-90 configuration, Table S11 reports the breakdown of thermal duties across all heat exchangers, while Table S12 provides the stream properties, including material balances for each process stream shown in Figure 5. In Table S11, negative values indicate cooling and positive values indicate heating.

Table S11. Heat exchangers thermal duty for the optimal cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90), detailed in Figure 5. Negative duty refers to cooling, positive duty refers to heating.

	Thermal duty [MW _{th}]
HX1	-6.089
HX2	-2.640
HX3	-5.498
HX4	-0.729
R1 COMP intercoolers	
Intercooler 1	-3.778
Intercooler 2	-3.036
Intercooler 3	-3.091
Intercooler 4	-3.166
Intercooler 5	-3.268
Intercooler 6	-3.407
Intercooler 7	-3.600
Intercooler 8	-3.869
e-HEATER	2.068
SLURRY COOLER	0.000
Stream #23	-18.970
Stream #40	18.970
MELTER	
Stream #25	10.591
Stream #43	-10.591
DIST Condenser	
Stream #29	-1.855
Stream #44	1.855
DIST Reboiler	
Stream #1	-3.430
Stream #32	3.430
MSHX	
Stream #7	-11.173
Stream #33	-3.491
Stream #38	-49.087
Stream #14	7.319
Stream #27	12.172
Stream #41	35.317
Stream #46	8.943

Table S12. Stream table of the optimal cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90), detailed in Figure 5.

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow	Process species [% mass]						Refrigerant species [% mass]			
	°C	bar			kg/s	CO ₂	O ₂	N ₂	Ar	H ₂ O	i-Pentane	Methane	Ethylene	Propane
1	110.0	1.000	Gas	91.71	31.8	7.2	53.1	0.9	7.1	0.0	-	-	-	-
2	74.4	0.980	Gas	91.71	31.8	7.2	53.1	0.9	7.1	0.0	-	-	-	-
3	35.0	0.968	Gas	88.13	33.1	7.4	55.2	0.9	3.3	0.0	-	-	-	-
4	77.6	1.444	Gas	88.13	33.1	7.4	55.2	0.9	3.3	0.0	-	-	-	-
5	35.0	1.415	Gas	88.13	33.1	7.4	55.2	0.9	3.3	0.0	-	-	-	-
6	17.5	1.398	Gas	85.87	33.9	7.6	56.7	1.0	0.8	0.0	-	-	-	-
7	45.1	1.048	Gas	85.18	34.2	7.7	57.1	1.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
8	-94.1	1.038	Gas	85.18	34.2	7.7	57.1	1.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
9	25.0	1.000	Liquid	112.85	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
10	50.8	1.006	Liquid	116.43	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
11	34.1	1.441	Liquid	51.59	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
12	34.1	1.441	Liquid	0.79	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
13	12.4	1.042	Liquid	50.12	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
14	-113.2	1.026	Gas	58.93	4.9	11.1	82.6	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
15	10.0	1.016	Gas	50.41	4.9	11.1	82.6	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
16	30.7	1.000	Gas	51.88	4.8	10.8	80.2	1.4	2.8	0.0	-	-	-	-
17	10.0	1.016	Gas	8.52	4.9	11.1	82.6	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
18	250.0	1.022	Gas	8.52	4.9	11.1	82.6	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
19	57.0	1.000	Gas	9.21	4.5	10.3	76.3	1.3	7.6	0.0	-	-	-	-
20	34.8	1.000	Gas	61.10	4.7	10.7	79.6	1.4	3.5	0.0	-	-	-	-
21	-121.1	1.060	Liquid	289.03	0.8	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.1	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.61	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
22	-94.4	1.038	Liquid	298.12	3.8	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	96.1	-	-	-	-
			Solid	17.77	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
23	-94.3	5.900	Liquid	298.20	3.8	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	96.1	-	-	-	-
			Solid	17.69	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
24	-124.0	5.700	Liquid	288.65	0.7	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.3	-	-	-	-
			Solid	27.24	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
25	-124.0	5.700	Liquid	14.43	0.7	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.3	-	-	-	-
			Solid	27.24	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
26	-58.0	5.500	Liquid	41.67	65.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	34.4	-	-	-	-
27	-57.2	24.100	Liquid	41.67	65.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	34.4	-	-	-	-
28	25.0	24.000	Gas	25.95	91.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.0	-	-	-	-
			Liquid	15.73	22.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	77.8	-	-	-	-
29	-13.1	24.000	Gas	26.27	99.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-	-	-	-
30	30.0	80.000	Liquid	26.27	99.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-	-	-	-
31	38.5	110.000	Liquid	26.27	99.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-	-	-	-
32	100.0	24.000	Liquid	15.40	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	92.9	-	-	-	-
33	30.0	23.800	Liquid	15.40	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	92.9	-	-	-	-
34	-83.1	23.700	Liquid	15.40	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	92.9	-	-	-	-

Table S12. Stream table of the optimal cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90), detailed in Figure 5 (continues from previous page).

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow	Process species [% mass]						Refrigerant species [% mass]			
	°C	bar			kg/s	CO ₂	O ₂	N ₂	Ar	H ₂ O	i-Pentane	Methane	Ethylene	Propane
35	-124.0	5.700	Liquid	274.21	0.7	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.3	-	-	-	-
36	20.0	1.060	Liquid	0.02	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	-	-	-	-
37	34.8	4.263	Gas	80.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	42.2	32.4	0.0	25.4
38	30.0	36.910	Gas	80.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	42.2	32.4	0.0	25.4
39	-101.0	36.810	Liquid	80.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	42.2	32.4	0.0	25.4
40	-129.0	4.563	Gas	14.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	96.8	3.2	0.0	0.0
			Liquid	66.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	30.3	38.8	0.0	30.9
41	-99.3	4.363	Gas	44.45	-	-	-	-	-	-	72.3	27.6	0.0	0.1
			Liquid	35.90	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.9	38.4	0.0	56.7
42	34.8	10.327	Gas	16.50	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.0
43	30.0	12.900	Gas	16.50	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.0
44	-100.0	12.700	Liquid	16.50	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.0
45	-80.2	12.500	Gas	2.61	-	-	-	-	-	-	60.5	39.5	0.0	0.0
			Liquid	13.88	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.4	87.6	0.0	0.0
46	-84.0	10.427	Gas	3.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	60.5	39.5	0.0	0.0
			Liquid	13.50	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.0	89.0	0.0	0.0

S8. Detailed energy and material balances for CCC-95

For the CCC-95 configuration, Table S13 reports the breakdown of thermal duties across all heat exchangers, while Table S14 provides the stream properties, including material balances for each process stream shown in Figure 5. In Table S13, negative values indicate cooling and positive values indicate heating.

Table S13. Heat exchangers thermal duty for the optimal cryogenic capture process at 95% capture rate (CCC-95), detailed in Figure 5. Negative duty refers to cooling, positive duty refers to heating.

	Thermal duty [MW _{th}]
HX1	-6.088
HX2	-2.643
HX3	-5.804
HX4	-0.773
R1 COMP intercoolers	
Intercooler 1	-4.055
Intercooler 2	-3.267
Intercooler 3	-3.323
Intercooler 4	-3.400
Intercooler 5	-3.507
Intercooler 6	-3.656
Intercooler 7	-3.868
Intercooler 8	-4.171
e-HEATER	-2.072
SLURRY COOLER	0.000
Stream #23	-20.317
Stream #40	20.317
MELTER	
Stream #25	11.182
Stream #43	-11.182
DIST Condenser	
Stream #29	-1.957
Stream #44	1.957
DIST Reboiler	
Stream #1	-3.433
Stream #32	3.433
MSHX	
Stream #7	-11.236
Stream #33	-3.494
Stream #38	-50.845
Stream #14	7.501
Stream #27	12.769
Stream #41	35.855
Stream #46	9.449

Table S14. Stream table of the optimal cryogenic capture process at 95% capture rate (CCC-95), detailed in Figure 5.

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow kg/s	Process species [% mass]						Refrigerant species [% mass]			
	°C	bar			CO ₂	O ₂	N ₂	Ar	H ₂ O	i-Pentane	Methane	Ethylene	Propane	n-Butane
1	110.0	1.000	Gas	91.71	31.8	7.2	53.1	0.9	7.1	0.0	-	-	-	-
2	74.4	0.980	Gas	91.71	31.8	7.2	53.1	0.9	7.1	0.0	-	-	-	-
3	35.0	0.968	Gas	88.13	33.1	7.4	55.2	0.9	3.3	0.0	-	-	-	-
4	77.6	1.443	Gas	88.13	33.1	7.4	55.2	0.9	3.3	0.0	-	-	-	-
5	35.0	1.415	Gas	88.13	33.1	7.4	55.2	0.9	3.3	0.0	-	-	-	-
6	17.8	1.398	Gas	85.88	33.9	7.6	56.7	1.0	0.8	0.0	-	-	-	-
7	45.9	1.048	Gas	85.17	34.2	7.7	57.1	1.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
8	-94.1	1.038	Gas	85.17	34.2	7.7	57.1	1.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
9	25.0	1.000	Liquid	112.87	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
10	50.8	1.006	Liquid	116.42	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
11	34.2	1.441	Liquid	51.75	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
12	34.2	1.441	Liquid	0.79	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
13	12.7	1.042	Liquid	50.29	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
14	-118.7	1.026	Gas	57.46	2.5	11.4	84.7	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
15	10.0	1.016	Gas	48.95	2.5	11.4	84.7	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
16	30.9	1.000	Gas	50.41	2.4	11.1	82.2	1.4	2.9	0.0	-	-	-	-
17	10.0	1.016	Gas	8.52	2.5	11.4	84.7	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
18	250.0	1.022	Gas	8.52	2.5	11.4	84.7	1.4	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
19	54.4	1.000	Gas	9.23	2.3	10.5	78.2	1.3	7.7	0.0	-	-	-	-
20	34.9	1.000	Gas	59.63	2.4	11.0	81.6	1.4	3.6	0.0	-	-	-	-
21	-123.5	1.060	Liquid	288.98	0.7	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.2	-	-	-	-
			Solid	0.66	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
22	-94.7	1.038	Liquid	298.25	3.8	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	96.2	-	-	-	-
			Solid	19.10	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
23	-94.5	5.900	Liquid	298.33	3.8	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	96.1	-	-	-	-
			Solid	19.02	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
24	-126.6	5.700	Liquid	288.63	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.4	-	-	-	-
			Solid	28.71	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
25	-126.6	5.700	Liquid	14.43	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.4	-	-	-	-
			Solid	28.71	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	-
26	-58.0	5.500	Liquid	43.15	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	33.2	-	-	-	-
27	-57.2	24.100	Liquid	43.15	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	33.2	-	-	-	-
28	25.0	24.000	Gas	27.57	91.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.0	-	-	-	-
			Liquid	15.58	22.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	77.8	-	-	-	-
29	-13.1	24.000	Gas	27.73	99.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-	-	-	-
30	30.0	80.000	Liquid	27.73	99.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-	-	-	-
31	38.5	110.000	Liquid	27.73	99.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-	-	-	-
32	100.0	24.000	Liquid	15.42	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	92.9	-	-	-	-
33	30.0	23.800	Liquid	15.42	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	92.9	-	-	-	-
34	-83.1	23.700	Liquid	15.42	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	92.9	-	-	-	-

Table S14. Stream table of the optimal cryogenic capture process at 95% capture rate (CCC-95), detailed in Figure 5 (continues from previous page).

Stream	T	P	Phase	Mass flow kg/s	Process species [% mass]						Refrigerant species [% mass]			
	°C	bar			CO ₂	O ₂	N ₂	Ar	H ₂ O	i-Pentane	Methane	Ethylene	Propane	n-Butane
35	-126.6	5.700	Liquid	274.20	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	99.4	-	-	-	-
36	20.0	1.060	Liquid	0.02	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	-	-	-	-
37	34.9	3.589	Gas	82.55	-	-	-	-	-	-	40.7	33.2	0.0	26.1
38	30.0	35.770	Gas	82.55	-	-	-	-	-	-	40.7	33.2	0.0	26.1
39	-102.5	35.670	Liquid	82.55	-	-	-	-	-	-	40.7	33.2	0.0	26.1
40	-131.6	3.889	Gas	15.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	97.0	3.0	0.0	0.0
			Liquid	67.54	-	-	-	-	-	-	28.2	39.9	0.0	31.9
41	-99.5	3.689	Gas	46.49	-	-	-	-	-	-	69.2	30.7	0.0	0.1
			Liquid	36.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.9	36.4	0.0	59.7
42	34.9	10.333	Gas	17.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.0
43	30.0	12.900	Gas	17.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.0
44	-100.0	12.700	Liquid	17.42	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.0
45	-80.2	12.500	Gas	2.76	-	-	-	-	-	-	60.5	39.5	0.0	0.0
			Liquid	14.66	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.4	87.6	0.0	0.0
46	-84.0	10.433	Gas	3.16	-	-	-	-	-	-	60.5	39.5	0.0	0.0
			Liquid	14.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	11.0	89.0	0.0	0.0

Nomenclature

Acronyms

CAPEX	Capital cost
CCC	Cryogenic CO ₂ capture
MSHX	Multi-stream heat exchanger
PR	Peng-Robinson
VTPR	Volume-translated Peng-Robinson

Symbols

α	—	α -function of cubic equations of state
β	W/m ³ /K	Local volumetric heat transfer coefficient for a stream
$\Delta H_{ads,H_2O}$	kJ/kg _{H₂O}	Heat of water adsorption
$\Delta H_{vap,H_2O}$	kJ/kg _{H₂O}	Heat of water vaporisation
ΔP	bar	Pressure drop
ΔT	K	Temperature difference
ΔT_{min}	K	Minimum temperature approach
ε	—	Bed porosity
ρ	kg/m ³	Density
μ	N · s/m ²	Viscosity
a	—	Parameter for equipment cost correlations
A_{exc}	m ²	Heat transfer area of heat exchanger
A_{pl}	m ²	Plate area
B_{exc}	W/m ³ /K	Overall volumetric heat transfer coefficient
BEC	€	Bare erected cost
c	—	Parameter of ideal gas heat capacity function
C_f	W/m ² /K	Fouling factor of heat exchanger
c_p	J/mol/K	Heat capacity
CP	W/K	Heat capacity flowrate
D	m	Diameter
EC	€	Equipment cost
f	—	Parameter for installation factor calculations
F_b	—	Saturated bed fraction
F_t	—	Log mean temperature correction factor

h	$\text{W/m}^2/\text{K}$	Film heat transfer coefficient of heat exchanger
H	kJ/kg	Mass enthalpy
$HETP$	m	Height equivalent theoretical plate
IF	–	Installation factor
j	–	Friction factor
k	W/m/K	Thermal conductivity
l	–	Parameter of α -function
L_{pl}	m	Plate length
$LMTD$	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Logarithmic mean temperature difference
\dot{m}	kg/s	Mass flowrate
m_b	kg	Adsorbent mass per bed
MF	–	Material Factor
N_b	–	Number of parallel beds in the adsorption stage
$N_{ch,pass}$	–	Number of channels per pass in plate heat exchangers
N_{pl}	–	Number of plates in plate heat exchangers
N_{tray}	–	Number of trays
$OPEX$	$\text{€}/\text{y}$	Operative costs
P	bar	Pressure
Pr	–	Prandtl dimensionless number
PF	–	Pressure Factor
$q_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{design}}$	$\text{kg}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/\text{kg}_{\text{adsorbent}}$	Water adsorption design capacity
\dot{Q}	W	Heat power exchanged
QF	–	Quantity Factor
Re	–	Reynolds dimensionless number
s_{pl}	m	Plate thickness
S_{pl}	m	Plate spacing
S_{tray}	m	Tray spacing
t_{ads}	s	Duration of the adsorption stage
T	K	Temperature
U_{exc}	$\text{W/m}^2/\text{K}$	Overall surface heat transfer coefficient
U^*	$\text{W/m}^2/\text{K}$	Tentative surface heat transfer coefficient
v	m/s	Velocity
V	m^3	Volume

\dot{V}	m^3/s	Volumetric flowrate
V_{exc}	m^3	Heat transfer volume of heat exchanger
w	—	Mass fraction
W_{pl}	m	Plate width
\dot{W}_{fluid}	W	Power delivered to the fluid
\dot{W}_{shaft}	W	Shaft power

Sub-/Superscripts

A	Adsorbate phase
ads	Adsorption
b	Bed
ch	Channel
cr	Critical
COLD	Cold side of multi-stream heat exchanger
cum	Cumulative
cz	Cold zone of multi-stream heat exchanger
el	Electric
eq	Equivalent
ext	External
G	Gas phase
gas	Gas
HOT	Hot side of multi-stream heat exchanger
hz	Hot zone of multi-stream heat exchanger
i	Generic species
ig	Ideal gas
IN	Inlet stream
int	Internal
k	Generic stream
liq	Liquid
mass	By mass
OUT	Outlet stream
p	Particle
pl	Plate
sat	Saturation
sh	Shell side
t	Tube side
th	Thermal
z	Global zone of multi-stream heat exchanger

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